

1 **Revised Manuscript**

2 **Decoding reach direction in early “visual” cortex of congenitally blind individuals**

3 Abbreviated title: Reach direction in the blind visual cortex

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23 **Conflict of interest statement**

24 The authors declare no competing interests.

25
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36

37

38 **Abstract**

39 Motor actions, such as reaching or grasping, can be decoded from fMRI activity of early
40 visual cortex in sighted humans. This effect can depend on vision or visual imagery, or
41 alternatively, could be driven by mechanisms independent of visual experience. Here, we
42 show that the actions of reaching in different directions can be reliably decoded from fMRI
43 activity of early visual cortex in congenitally blind humans (both sexes). Thus, neither visual
44 experience nor visual imagery is necessary for early visual cortex to represent action-related
45 information. We also demonstrate that, within early visual cortex of blind humans, the
46 accuracy of reach direction decoding is highest in areas typically representing foveal vision
47 and gradually decreases in areas typically representing peripheral vision. We propose that
48 this might indicate the existence of a predictive, hard-wired mechanism of aligning action
49 and visual spaces. This mechanism might send action-related information primarily to the
50 high-resolution foveal visual areas, which are critical for guiding and online correction of
51 motor actions. Finally, we show that, beyond early visual cortex, the decoding of reach
52 direction in blind humans is most accurate in dorsal stream areas known to be critical for
53 visuo-spatial and visuo-motor integration in the sighted. Thus, these areas can develop
54 space and action representations even in the lifelong absence of vision. Overall, our findings
55 in congenitally blind humans match previous research on the action system in the sighted,
56 and suggest that the development of action representations in the human brain might be
57 largely independent of visual experience.

58

59 **Significance Statement**

60 Early visual cortex (EVC) was traditionally thought to process only visual signals from the
61 retina. Recent studies proved this account incomplete, and showed EVC involvement in
62 many activities not directly related to incoming visual information, such as memory, sound,
63 or action processing. Is EVC involved in these activities because of visual imagery? Here,

64 we show robust reach direction representation in EVC of humans born blind. This
65 demonstrates that EVC can represent actions independently of vision and visual imagery.
66 Beyond EVC, we found that reach direction representation in blind humans is strongest in
67 dorsal brain areas, critical for action processing in the sighted. This suggests that the
68 development of action representations in the human brain is largely independent of visual
69 experience.

70

71 **Introduction**

72 Early visual cortex (EVC) was traditionally considered a purely perceptual region, which only
73 processes visual signals from the retina. Recent years proved this account incomplete, with
74 studies demonstrating that EVC is involved in many activities that are not directly related to
75 incoming visual information, such as working memory (Harrison and Tong, 2009; Roelfsema
76 and de Lange, 2016), sound representation (Vetter et al., 2014), or action representation
77 (Monaco et al., 2020; Knights et al., 2021). However, it is still debated whether EVC
78 involvement in these tasks can be reduced to visual imagery.

79 Studying individuals born blind, who could not develop visual imagery, is a powerful way to
80 contribute to this debate. Here, we used this approach to investigate how EVC represents
81 motor actions. This region increases its activity when sighted individuals plan or perform
82 motor actions, such as reaching toward objects or grasping them (Monaco et al., 2017;
83 Strykowiec et al., 2019). This effect persists even when actions are performed in darkness
84 (Monaco et al., 2017). Furthermore, EVC activity in sighted individuals can be used to
85 distinguish between specific actions or action intentions (Monaco et al., 2020; Knights et al.,
86 2021). One interpretation of these findings is that the emergence of action representation in
87 EVC is driven by visual imagery: the creation of internal, vision-like mental representation of
88 actions or objects over which actions are performed (Pearson et al., 2015). An intriguing,
89 alternative hypothesis is that EVC can represent action-related information independently of

90 visual experience. One can suppose, for example, that spatial properties of actions or action
91 targets can be mapped onto the EVC retinotopic organization without being transformed into
92 visual format. Several studies have shown that the EVC retinotopic organization is used to
93 represent certain types of information even in congenitally blind individuals (Striem-Amit et
94 al., 2015; Norman and Thaler, 2019; Vetter et al., 2020).

95 In sighted individuals, performing actions over small objects preferentially involves EVC
96 foveal areas, even when participants do not see these objects and fixate on a point well
97 above their location (Monaco et al., 2017). Beyond visual cortex, motor actions primarily
98 involve dorsal brain regions, such as the motor and somatosensory cortices, the superior
99 parietal lobe (SPL), the intraparietal sulcus (IPS), and the frontal eye field/dorsal premotor
100 cortex (FEF/PMd) (Fabbri et al., 2014; Gallivan and Culham, 2015). Here, we used these
101 findings as leverage to study the impact of vision on the action system development.
102 Particularly, an observation that actions preferentially involve typically foveal EVC also in
103 congenitally blind individuals would be suggestive of similar neural mechanisms supporting
104 action-related representations in EVC in both populations. Furthermore, finding that actions
105 preferentially involve dorsal stream regions also in congenitally blind individuals would add to
106 evidence that these regions can develop relatively typical functional specialization
107 independently of visual experience (Garg et al., 2007; Fiehler et al., 2009; Striem-Amit et al.,
108 2012).

109 We used functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) to measure brain activity in nine
110 congenitally blind participants who reached for and read Braille words printed on the four
111 cardinal positions (up, down, left, right) of an A4 Braille sheet. We then used multi-voxel
112 pattern classification to decode different reach directions from these participants' brain
113 activity. Importantly, different, unrelated Braille words were used in the two experimental
114 runs. This, in combination with our analytical scheme (training and testing the classifier on
115 different runs; see Materials and Methods), ensured that we investigated representation of
116 reach directions, rather than representation of Braille words (Sadato et al., 1996; Cohen et

117 al., 1997). Devoid of all features specific to a given word, our Braille stimuli could be seen as
118 a form of small objects, requiring a very precise calibration of the reach and the hand shape.
119 We expected to find reach direction representation in EVC of the blind participants,
120 particularly in typically foveal areas. Beyond EVC, we expected to find reach direction
121 representation primarily in regions that form the action system in the sighted.

122

123 **Materials and Methods**

124 ***Participants***

125 Nine congenitally blind individuals with intact hearing (3 males, 6 females, mean age 33
126 years, range 23-39 years, 4 left handers, 4 right handers, 1 ambidextrous, mean education
127 duration 14 years, range 12-17 years) participated in the study. Reasons for blindness were:
128 microphthalmia in three participants of which one also had retinal detachment, retinopathy of
129 prematurity in four participants, enophthalmos in one participant, and Leber congenital
130 amaurosis in one participant. One blind participant had very faint light perception, all others
131 had no light perception at all. All participants were proficient Braille readers. Eight out of nine
132 participants participated in our previous study on natural sound decoding from EVC activity
133 (Vetter et al., 2020). In this previous study, such a sample size was sufficient to detect robust
134 effects in early visual areas. Here, we expected to obtain effects of comparable size. All
135 participants received detailed information on the study, signed informed consent, and were
136 paid for their participation. The study was approved by the Tel-Aviv Sourasky Medical Center
137 Ethics Committee, Israel.

138 ***Experimental design***

139 The design of the experiment is illustrated in Fig. 1. Participants underwent fMRI while they
140 were reaching for and reading Braille words printed at the center of the four edges of a thick
141 A4 Braille sheet (portrait orientation) to probe the four cardinal spatial positions (up, down,

142 left, and right) (Fig 1A). Two different Braille sheets with different, unrelated words referring
143 to abstract concepts with low imagination score were used to ensure that the subsequent
144 multi-voxel pattern classification analysis did not rely on the processing of word meanings.
145 The Braille sheets were handed to participants by the experimenter and exchanged for the
146 other Braille sheet after each run. Order of Braille sheets was counterbalanced across
147 participants. Participants lay supine inside the MRI scanner, held the Braille sheet with their
148 non-dominant hand flat on their lap and started each experimental trial with the index finger
149 of their dominant hand on a central “fixation” dot printed on the Braille sheet. Then, they
150 heard a verbal cue indicating the reach direction (“up”, “down”, “left” or “right”, approximately
151 1 s), which was followed by 3.5 s of silence to allow for hand reaching and word reading at
152 the cued location (4.5 s of a trial time, in total; Fig 1B). Participants moved their hand and
153 lower arm from the center ~14 cm towards the up and down locations and ~9 cm towards
154 the left and right locations (within the dimension of an A4 sheet). Subsequently, participants
155 heard a second verbal cue (approximately 1 s) instructing them to return their hands to the
156 center of the Braille sheet, which was followed by silence lasting for 8 s (9 s of a rest time, in
157 total).

158 Subjects completed 2 runs, each consisting of 40 trials (10 trials x 4 reach directions). The
159 order of trials was randomized with a constraint that the same reach direction did not repeat
160 in two consecutive trials.

161 We used Braille words as reach targets, instead of more typical “objects”, mostly for practical
162 reasons - such stimuli could be squeezed into an A4 sheet and comfortably reached in a
163 constrained MRI scanner space, without the need to build special platforms, which are
164 usually used for the presentation of more typical objects (e.g., Singhal et al., 2013; Monaco
165 et al., 2017, 2020). Moreover, our pilot study suggested that keeping participants’ reaches
166 relatively short – a study feature that we could readily achieve with Braille words - attenuated
167 the fMRI signal artifacts related to moving in the MRI scanner (Barry et al., 2010) and
168 resulted in overall better data quality. Last but not least, reaching for and reading Braille

169 words was a very natural activity for the blind participants enrolled in the study, and made
170 the experimental task readily understandable for them.

171 ***Data collection***

172 Blood oxygen level dependent signals were acquired in a 3 T General Electric MRI scanner
173 with an 8-channel head coil (TR = 1.5 s, TE = 35 ms, Resolution: $3.75 \times 3.75 \times 4.5$ mm
174 voxels, 4.5 mm slice thickness, 0.4 mm gap thickness, 27 slices, flip angle: 70). In each
175 experimental run, 376 volumes were collected. Additionally, an anatomical brain image was
176 collected for each participant using a standard MPRAGE T1-weighted sequence.

177 ***Data preprocessing***

178 Data were analyzed in BrainVoyager 20.6 (BrainInnovation). Standard preprocessing
179 routines were used, including slice scan time correction, 3D rigid body motion correction,
180 temporal high-pass filter (GLM with Fourier basis set, 3 cycles per run), no spatial smoothing
181 for the multi-voxel pattern analysis, and spatial smoothing on cortical surface (the nearest
182 neighbors approach, repeat value: 4) for the univariate analysis. Activation for each trial (in
183 the multi-voxel pattern analysis: 2 runs x 4 reach directions x 10 trials) or experimental
184 condition (in the univariate analysis: 2 runs x 4 reach directions) was modeled using a
185 general linear model by convolving each trial/condition time course with the canonical
186 hemodynamic response function. For each participant, functional data were mapped onto an
187 individual reconstruction of the cortical surface, created based on the collected anatomical
188 image. All subsequent analyses were performed in the surface space.

189 ***Statistical analysis***

190 ***Multi-voxel pattern classification (decoding) analysis.*** All multi-voxel pattern
191 classification analyses were performed in CosmoMvpa (v.1.1.0; Oosterhof et al., 2016),
192 running on Matlab R2018b (MathWorks). All analyses were performed on T-values (Misaki et
193 al., 2010). To obtain these values, a separate T-map was computed for each experimental
194 trial by comparing brain activation during this trial to brain activation during rest periods in a

195 given run (10 trials x 4 reach directions per run, 80 maps per participant in total). In all
196 analyses, a linear support vector machine classification algorithm was used, as implemented
197 in the LIBSVM toolbox (v. 3.23; Chang and Lin, 2001). A standard LIBSVM data
198 normalization procedure (i.e., Z-scoring beta estimates for each voxel in the training set and
199 applying output values to the test set) was applied to the data before classification.

200 We performed several multi-voxel pattern classification analyses in EVC. We used the same,
201 bilateral EVC patches of interest (POIs) as in our previous study investigating natural sound
202 representations in the same blind participants (Vetter et al., 2020). Briefly, a standard
203 retinotopic polar mapping fMRI experiment was performed to delineate areas V1, V2, and V3
204 in 10 sighted participants (data reported in Vetter et al., 2014). These areas were also
205 divided into three equally spaced segments along the posterior-anterior brain axis, to create
206 POIs representing approximately foveal, peripheral, and far peripheral visual fields
207 (eccentricity mapping was not performed). Then, the individual POIs obtained from sighted
208 participants were mapped onto a cortical surface reconstruction of each blind participant,
209 using the BrainVoyager cortex-based alignment procedure, and converted into maximum
210 probability maps (Fig. 1C), which were then used in the classification analyses.

211 Importantly, a standard retinotopic mapping fMRI experiment, as the one described here, is
212 not able to image the whole visual field in humans (see Pitzalis et al., 2006, for discussion).
213 Thus, our “far periphery” EVC POIs are unlikely to correspond to the real-live boundaries of
214 the visual field. Nevertheless, the obtained POIs extended into fairly anterior portions of the
215 calcarine sulcus and the pericalcarine cortex (see Fig. 1C), which suggests that the
216 peripheral visual representation was stimulated (perhaps not only directly, but also through
217 lateral connections; Pitzalis et al., 2006).

218 In the first analysis, we tested for the EVC representation of reach direction in each blind
219 participant separately (within-participant decoding). Thus, the cross-validation of the
220 classification results was performed across runs - in each participant, there were two cross-
221 validation folds, and in each of them one run was used to train the classifier and the other

222 run was used for testing. This cross-validation scheme ensured that we decoded reach
223 direction rather than Braille words, which were different in each run (i.e., in the training and
224 testing sets; see also Experimental Design). We tested for the reach direction representation
225 in the whole EVC (areas V1, V2, and V3 combined) and in each early visual area separately.
226 Additionally, we also tested for reach direction representation in the two other early sensory
227 regions: motor cortex and auditory cortex. The auditory cortex POI was created by
228 combining the bilateral masks of Brodmann areas (BAs) 41 and 42 together. The motor
229 cortex POI was defined as bilateral area BA 4 (thus, it is likely to contain the somatotopic
230 map of the whole body, not only the hand or arm). The BrainVoyager and BrainTutor
231 (BrainInnovation, Maastricht) cortical atlases were used to obtain the masks of specific BAs.
232 The atlases were cortex-based aligned to the reconstruction of cortical surfaces of blind
233 participants using the procedures described above.

234 Second, we tested for the generalization of the activity patterns induced by specific reach
235 directions across the blind participants (cross-participant decoding). This analysis was again
236 performed in the three sensory regions: EVC, motor cortex, and auditory cortex. The aim of
237 this analysis was to test if reach direction representation might rely on the large-scale
238 organization of these regions (e.g., retinotopy in EVC, somatotopy in motor cortex), as only
239 such representation is likely to be generalized across participants. To verify this, the cross-
240 validation of reach direction classification was performed across participants – that is, there
241 were nine cross-validation folds, and in each of them the data from eight participants were
242 used to train the classifier and the data from the remaining participant were used for testing.
243 For the cross-participant analysis, the sensory POIs were defined as was described above,
244 and aligned to the average cortical folding of all blind participants using a group cortex-
245 based alignment procedure. This resulted in exactly the same POIs for each participant. As
246 an additional control analysis, we used the same POIs and cross-participant analysis
247 scheme to try to decode the two sets of Braille words, which were reached and read by the
248 blind participants in the two experimental runs. We reasoned that even if EVC in blind

249 participants represents some information related to abstract Braille words, which were used
250 as a target for reaches in our study (Sadato et al., 1996, Cohen et al., 1997), such
251 representation is unlikely to rely on large-scale retinotopic biases that could be generalized
252 across the participants.

253 Third, we investigated the reach direction representation in EVC areas that, in sighted
254 individuals, represent foveal and peripheral vision. The analysis was performed in foveal,
255 peripheral, and far peripheral EVC POIs (see above for their description). The results for
256 similar POIs delineated in specific visual areas (V1, V2, and V3) were also calculated. The
257 within-participant decoding and across-run cross validation scheme, described above, were
258 used. Furthermore, to exclude a possibility that differences in foveal, peripheral, and far
259 peripheral POI sizes (average foveal POI = 684 vertices; average peripheral POI = 912
260 vertices; average far peripheral POI = 1048 vertices) affected our results, we repeated the
261 analysis while randomly drawing (without replacement) equal numbers of vertices from
262 foveal, peripheral, and far peripheral EVC POIs. We tested six POI sizes, from 100 to 600
263 vertices. At each POI size level, and for each of the three POIs, we averaged the decoding
264 results across 1000 random draws of vertices. We then compared the results with the
265 decoding accuracies obtained in the analysis of whole POIs.

266 Fourth, to further investigate the robustness of our findings, we plotted decoding accuracies
267 obtained for individual blind participants. The results for EVC, motor cortex, and auditory
268 cortex POIs were plotted.

269 In addition to the analyses focused on EVC, we performed the searchlight analysis, to reveal
270 the whole cortical network representing reach direction in the blind participants. The
271 analysis was performed on cortical surface reconstructions of each blind participant, using
272 CosmoMOPA and Surfing Toolbox (Oosterhof et al., 2011). It was performed separately for
273 each hemisphere, within surface patches containing 100 vertices. All other analysis
274 parameters were the same as in the within-participant POI decoding analyses.

275 Finally, to test if the reach decoding representation is stronger in canonical visuospatial
276 processing areas than in other high-order brain areas, we performed the within-participant
277 POI analysis, using the parameters described above, in four regions: the two canonical
278 visuospatial areas, that is, inferior parietal sulcus, (IPS) and frontal eye field/dorsal premotor
279 cortex (FEF/PMd), and the two canonical language areas, the Broca's area and the superior
280 temporal sulcus/superior temporal gyrus (STS/STG). The Broca's area POI was created by
281 combining left BAs 44 and 45 together. The STS/STG POI was defined as left BA 22. As in
282 the previous analyses, the BrainVoyager cortical atlas of Brodmann areas was used to
283 define these POIs. The IPS POI was defined bilaterally using the BrainVoyager atlas of
284 cortical sulci. It covered the whole extent of the IPS - thus, it is likely to include multiple
285 functional areas (e.g., Gallivan and Culham, 2015). Our aim was to have a general
286 assessment of the reach direction decoding accuracy in the IPS, rather than to distinguish
287 between these specific areas. The FEF/PMd POI was defined bilaterally using BrainVoyager
288 "fMRI atlas", and then dilated to achieve the approximate size of the Broca's and the
289 STS/STG POIs. The procedures of cortex-based alignment, identical to those used in the
290 other within-participant POI analyses, were used to align each POI to cortical reconstructions
291 of individual blind participants.

292 In all within-participant POI decoding analyses, the statistical significance of obtained
293 classification accuracies was tested against chance levels that were empirically derived in
294 the permutation procedure. Specifically, each classification analysis was re-run 1000 times
295 for each participant with reach direction labels (up, down, right, left) randomly assigned to
296 experimental trials in each iteration, participant, and experimental run. Null distributions
297 created in this procedure were averaged across participants and compared with the actual
298 average classification accuracies. The P-values that were obtained in this way were
299 corrected for multiple comparisons using the false discovery rate (FDR; Benjamini and
300 Hochberg 1995). A review of null distributions confirmed that, for each POI and analysis, the

301 empirically-derived chance levels were indistinguishable from a priori chance levels (25 %).
302 Thus, for simplicity, the a priori chance level is presented in the figures.

303 The same procedures were used in the cross-participant decoding analysis. In the case of
304 cross-participant reach direction decoding, the chance level was derived by re-running the
305 analysis with reach direction labels (up, down, right, left) randomly assigned to experimental
306 trials in each iteration, participant, and run, as was described above. In the case of cross-
307 participant Braille words decoding, the analysis was re-run with labels of the two Braille
308 sheets randomly assigned to experimental runs, in each iteration and participant. Also in the
309 cross-participant analysis, the empirically-derived chance levels were indistinguishable from
310 a priori chance levels (25 % for reach direction decoding, 50 % for Braille words decoding).

311 Testing for significant differences in decoding accuracies across multiple POIs was
312 performed with repeated-measures ANOVAs. Testing for differences in decoding accuracies
313 between two POIs was performed with a paired t-test. SPSS 25 (IBM Corp, Armonk, NY)
314 was used to perform these tests. FDR was used to correct for multiple comparisons, when
315 applicable.

316 To statistically test for above-chance effects in the searchlight analysis, single-subject
317 classification accuracy maps were smoothed (a BrainVoyager procedure of smoothing on
318 surface, the nearest neighbors approach, repeat value: 4), cortex-based aligned to the group
319 average, and converted into a group threshold-free cluster enhancement (TFCE) map (Smith
320 and Nichols 2009), calculated in CosmoMVPA with standard parameters ($E = 0.5$, $H = 2$).
321 The obtained TFCE values were then compared with an empirically-derived chance level,
322 obtained in the Monte Carlo simulation procedure (Oosterhof et al., 2016). Specifically, for
323 each vertex, the TFCE values obtained in the group analysis of actual decoding accuracies
324 were compared with the null distribution of TFCE values obtained in 10000 iterations in
325 which the signs of the effects obtained in specific participants were randomly flipped. The
326 analysis was thresholded at $p < 0.05$, corrected for multiple comparisons across the whole
327 cortical surface of a given hemisphere ($z = 1.65$).

328 **Univariate analysis.** We also ran the univariate analysis, to reveal brain responses elicited
329 by our task, relative to rest periods, in the congenitally blind participants. We first performed
330 a whole-brain analysis, in which we tested for activations induced by all experimental trials,
331 compared to rest, across the cortical surface. This was followed by a more sensitive POI
332 analysis, in which we investigated the same effect in EVC, in specific early visual areas (V1,
333 V2, and V3), and in the EVC regions that typically represent specific visual eccentricities
334 (foveal, peripheral, and far peripheral; see above for the description of these POIs).

335 Furthermore, we also tested for univariate activation differences across the experimental
336 conditions, that is, trials with different reach directions (up, down, right, left). To perform the
337 whole-brain analysis, contrast estimate maps for each experimental condition versus rest
338 were calculated for each participant (4 maps for each participant), using BrainVoyager GLM
339 functionality. These maps were then entered into a repeated-measures ANOVA, as
340 implemented in CosmoMOPA. The whole brain analysis was again followed by a POI
341 analysis in EVC.

342 All univariate analyses were performed on smoothed data (see Data Preprocessing). The
343 statistical significance of effects observed in the whole-brain univariate analyses was again
344 tested using TFCE maps and Monte Carlo simulation, as implemented in CosmoMOPA. The
345 same analysis parameters and statistical thresholds as in the searchlight decoding analysis
346 were used. The statistical significance of effects observed in the POI analyses was tested
347 using one-sample t-tests. The differences between results for different POIs were tested
348 using repeated-measures ANOVAs and paired-sample t-tests. SPSS 25 was used to
349 calculate all statistics in the univariate POI analyses. FDR correction for multiple
350 comparisons was applied, when applicable.

351 **Controlling for movement artifacts.** Finally, we run several control analyses to exclude the
352 possibility that our results are driven by the fMRI signal artifacts induced by movements
353 performed in the MRI scanner (Barry et al., 2010).

354 First, we investigated event-related average plots, illustrating the unfolding of brain activation
355 for all experimental trials compared to rest, for the four regions that are critical for the study:
356 EVC, motor cortex, IPS, and FEF/PMd. The plots were calculated separately for each
357 hemisphere, using the POIs described above, and then averaged. We performed this
358 analysis to verify if there were any spikes in the signal when participants performed the
359 reaches. The existence of such spikes would be indicative of movement-related artifacts in
360 the signal (e.g., Singhal et al., 2013; Monaco et al., 2017).

361 Second, we ran the within-participant decoding of reach directions in the frontal white matter,
362 near motor cortex. Contrary to the actual analyses, this analysis was performed in volume
363 space, as decoding only from the white matter is not possible in the surface space. The
364 region of interest was defined in the right hemisphere (Talairach coordinates of the center:
365 21, 16, 29) and contained approximately 50 voxels. The statistical significance of the
366 decoding was assessed in the permutation procedure, in the same way as in the actual
367 analyses.

368 Third, we further analyzed the results produced by the searchlight classification procedure.
369 Specifically, we averaged the reach decoding accuracies produced by the searchlight within
370 each of our four critical POIs (EVC, Motor cortex, IPS, FEF/PMd). Next, we compared these
371 accuracies with searchlight reach decoding accuracy averaged across the frontal and
372 temporal lobes (the motor cortex and the FEF/PMd were excluded from the mask).
373 Furthermore, we re-ran the searchlight decoding analysis, and we tested for significant
374 effects (using the same procedures and thresholds as in the original analysis) using the
375 mean decoding accuracy obtained within the above-described, frontal and temporal mask as
376 baseline. The frontal and temporal regions are likely to include some “ground-truth”
377 representations of reach directions, and are also among most affected by movement
378 artifacts (Wu et al., 1997; Barry et al., 2010). Thus, finding significant effects in these
379 analyses, in regions that are critical for our claims, would be a conservative demonstration of

380 (1) specificity of our effects, and (2) that our findings cannot be explained by movement
381 artifacts.

382

383 **Results**

384 ***Multi-voxel pattern classification (decoding) results***

385 In the within-participant decoding analysis, we were able to reliably decode reach direction
386 (up, down, left, right) from fMRI activity patterns of EVC (areas V1, V2 and V3 combined)
387 and of specific early visual areas in the congenitally blind participants (all p s < 0.001, Fig. 2).
388 Successful decoding of reach direction was also achieved in other sensory areas - motor
389 cortex and auditory cortex (all p s < 0.001; Fig 2). However, the accuracy of reach direction
390 decoding in these three sensory areas differed, as indicated by a significant area effect ($F(2,$
391 $16) = 12.11, p < 0.001, \text{partial eta-squared} = 0.6$) in a one-way repeated-measures ANOVA.
392 The post-hoc comparisons revealed a higher decoding accuracy in motor cortex than in
393 auditory cortex ($p = 0.001$) and EVC (trend level, $p = 0.052$). Moreover, the decoding
394 accuracy in EVC was higher than in auditory cortex (trend level, $p = 0.052$).

395 In the cross-participant decoding analysis, we were able to decode reach directions across
396 participants in EVC ($p = 0.003$) and in motor cortex ($p = 0.003$), but not in auditory cortex (p
397 $= 0.189$) (Fig. 3A). This suggests that the reach direction in EVC and in motor cortex is
398 represented using some form of a large-scale organization (e.g., retinotopy in EVC,
399 somatotopy in motor cortex), as only such organization is likely to generalize across
400 participants. In contrast to the reach direction decoding, we were not able to decode the two
401 sets of Braille words used in the study across the blind participants, in any of the three
402 sensory areas (all p s > 0.25; Fig. 3B).

403 In the within-participant analysis of typically foveal and peripheral EVC areas, we observed a
404 gradient of reach direction decoding accuracy at different eccentricities (Fig. 4). As expected,
405 the decoding was most accurate in the foveal parts of EVC and gradually decreased in

406 peripheral parts of this region, as indicated by a significant eccentricity effect ($F(2, 16) =$
407 $3.77, p = 0.046, \text{partial } \eta\text{-squared} = 0.32$) and a significant linear contrast for the
408 eccentricity factor ($F(1, 8) = 5.64, p = 0.045, \text{partial } \eta\text{-squared} = 0.41$) in a one-way
409 repeated-measures ANOVA.

410 We then repeated the analysis in POIs created by randomly drawing an equal number of
411 vertices from foveal, peripheral, and far peripheral EVC POIs (see Materials and Methods).
412 We created POIs including from 100 to 600 vertices and observed comparable foveal-
413 peripheral reach direction decoding gradient across all POI sizes tested (Fig. 5). The 3 (EVC
414 eccentricity) x 7 (POI size, including the whole POIs) repeated-measures ANOVA produced
415 a significant main effect of POI size ($F(6, 96) = 15.07, p = 0.002, \text{partial } \eta\text{-squared} = 0.65$),
416 indicating that the decoding accuracy increased with larger POI sizes. Importantly, we also
417 found a significant main effect of EVC eccentricity ($F(2, 96) = 3.95, p = 0.040, \text{partial } \eta\text{-}$
418 $\text{squared} = 0.33$) and a significant linear contrast for this effect ($F(1, 8) = 5.77, p = 0.043,$
419 $\text{partial } \eta\text{-squared} = 0.42$). There were no interactions between the two main effects ($F < 1,$
420 $p > 0.25$). Overall, this control analysis shows that the foveal-peripheral reach direction
421 decoding gradient can be reliably found in EVC in congenitally blind participants across
422 variety of POI sizes, and when the size differences between specific POIs are controlled.

423 Furthermore, given that in our previous study (Vetter et al., 2020) we observed an opposing
424 EVC decoding accuracy gradient (i.e., better decoding in peripheries) when the same blind
425 participants listened to natural sounds, we formally tested for a difference in these results.
426 We entered the EVC decoding accuracies obtained in our two studies in a 2 (study) x 3
427 (EVC eccentricity) repeated-measures ANOVA. As expected, we found highly significant
428 interactions between study and EVC eccentricity factors ($F(2, 14) = 31.26, p < 0.001, \text{partial}$
429 $\eta\text{-squared} = 0.82$), and between study and linear contrasts fitted to the EVC eccentricity
430 factor ($F(1, 7) = 84.18, p < 0.001, \text{partial } \eta\text{-squared} = 0.92$).

431 We then plotted the within-participant decoding results for individual participants (Fig. 6). We
432 found that the accuracy of reach direction decoding in EVC was above chance level in all

433 nine congenitally blind participants. Furthermore, the foveal-peripheral reach direction
434 decoding gradient in EVC was clearly visible even at the level of individual results.

435 In the surface searchlight analysis (Fig. 7), we observed the highest reach decoding
436 accuracy in the foveal parts of EVC and in the dorsal brain areas: motor and somatosensory
437 cortices, superior parietal lobule (SPL), intraparietal sulcus (IPS), supplementary motor area
438 (SMA), and right frontal eye field/dorsal premotor cortex (FEF/PMd). The independent POI
439 analysis confirmed that reach decoding accuracy in EVC and in the two canonical dorsal
440 visuospatial areas (IPS and FEF/PMd) was significantly higher than in the two canonical
441 language areas (Broca's area and left STS/STG) (Fig. 8; all p s < 0.05). These results
442 suggest that the dorsal stream regions are preferentially involved in representing reach-
443 related information in congenitally blind participants. Moreover, this analysis provides an
444 important control comparison: the fact that the decoding accuracy for reach direction was
445 higher in EVC than in auditory cortex (Fig. 2) and in canonical language regions (Fig. 8)
446 shows that the effects observed in EVC cannot be explained by auditory or linguistic
447 processing of the verbal cues indicating reach direction in each trial.

448 ***Univariate results***

449 In the whole-brain, fully-corrected analysis we did not observe any significant activations for
450 our task, compared to rest, perhaps because our event-related design was optimized for the
451 decoding rather than detecting univariate brain responses. However, with a more lenient
452 statistical threshold ($p < 0.001$, uncorrected), we were able to detect expected activations in
453 the motor, somatosensory, and parietal cortices (Fig. 9A). Furthermore, a more sensitive
454 POI analysis revealed a subtle univariate response in EVC ($t(8) = 1.96$, $p = 0.043$; Fig. 9B).
455 The univariate responses in EVC increased from typically peripheral to typically foveal
456 regions (Main effect of EVC eccentricity: $F(2, 16) = 4.93$, $p = 0.048$, partial eta-squared =
457 0.38; linear contrast: $F(1, 8) = 6.46$, $p = 0.035$; partial eta-squared = 0.45; Fig. 9C), an effect
458 similar to the one found for the decoding accuracies. Interestingly, univariate responses also
459 increased from V1 to V3 (Main effect of area: $F(2, 16) = 7.65$, $p = 0.005$, partial eta-squared

460 = 0.49; linear contrast: $F(1, 8) = 8.25$, $p = 0.021$, partial eta-squared = 0.51; Fig. 9D), an
461 effect not found for the decoding accuracies, which were comparable in all early visual
462 areas. Our task did not elicit a univariate response in area V1 ($t < 1$, $p > 0.25$), which showed
463 robust reach direction representation in the decoding analysis.

464 The whole-brain analysis of differences in activations across specific reach directions (up,
465 down, right, left) produced significant effects in left motor and somatosensory cortices, left
466 inferior frontal cortex, medial frontal cortices, temporal lobe, precuneus, and cuneus (Fig.
467 10A). Given that some of these effects were localized in regions in which no significant
468 responses relative to rest were observed (including some default mode network regions:
469 Raichle, 2015), we cannot exclude the possibility that these findings reflect differences in
470 deactivation levels rather than in above-rest activations. In a more sensitive POI analysis, we
471 also detected a significant main effect of experimental condition (reach direction) in EVC
472 ($F(3, 24) = 3.29$, $p = 0.038$, partial eta-squared = 0.29). While a pattern of responses
473 induced by each condition, relative to rest, suggested that EVC activations were primarily
474 driven by trials in which the participants reached down ($t(8) = 3.65$, $p = 0.014$; ps for all other
475 conditions > 0.1 ; Fig. 10B), the direct comparisons between experimental conditions were
476 not significant (all $ps > 0.05$).

477 ***Controlling for movement artifacts***

478 The analysis of event-related average plots did not show signal spikes at the moment of
479 hand movement, similar to those described previously (e.g., Singhal et al., 2013; Monaco et
480 al., 2017), in any of the four regions tested (EVC, motor cortex, IPS, and FEF/PMd; Fig.
481 11A). The accuracy of within-participant decoding of reach directions in the frontal white
482 matter was not significantly different from chance level ($p = 0.107$; Fig. 11B). Finally, testing
483 for significant effects in the searchlight analysis performed with decoding accuracy in frontal
484 and temporal regions as baseline (see Material and Methods) still produced significant
485 results in the foveal EVC, motor and somatosensory cortices, SMA, IPS, and FEF/PMd (Fig.
486 11C). These effects were detected despite the fact that frontal and temporal regions are

487 amongst most affected by movement artifacts (Wu et al., 1997; Barry et al., 2010), and are
488 also likely to compute some “ground-truth” reach direction representations.

489 Overall, the three analyses that were performed provide converging evidence that our results
490 cannot be explained by movement artifacts.

491

492 **Discussion**

493 In this study, we found that reach direction could be reliably decoded from fMRI activity
494 patterns of early visual cortex (EVC) in congenitally blind participants. We also observed a
495 gradient of reach direction decoding within EVC in these participants – the decoding
496 accuracy was highest in the typically foveal EVC areas and gradually decreased in typically
497 peripheral areas. Beyond EVC, the reach direction decoding was most accurate in dorsal
498 brain areas, such as somatosensory and motor cortices, SPL, IPS, SMA, or FEF/PMd.

499 Are representations of motor actions, observed in EVC of sighted individuals (Monaco et al.,
500 2020; Knights et al., 2021), reducible to visual imagery? Is vision a necessary prerequisite
501 for the development of these representations? The answers to these questions were unclear
502 and inferred primarily from differences in response magnitudes during actions and imagining
503 actions (Monaco et al., 2017), or from null effects in cross-decoding between these two
504 conditions (Monaco et al., 2020). Here, we took a different approach to resolve these issues
505 - we tested congenitally blind participants, who have never had visual experience and could
506 not develop visual imagery. Our results clearly demonstrate that neither visual experience
507 nor visual imagery - understood as the creation of an internal, vision-like mental
508 representation of actions or objects over which actions are performed - is necessary for the
509 emergence of action-related representation in EVC.

510 If action-related information is not represented in EVC through visual imagery, then what
511 mechanisms can support such representation? One possibility is that spatial properties of
512 actions or action targets (“objects”) can be directly projected onto EVC retinotopic

513 organization, without an intermediate step of being transformed into visual format. Our
514 results support this possibility and suggest that the retinotopic EVC organization is, indeed,
515 involved in representing reach directions in blind individuals. First, we were able to cross-
516 decode reach directions across the blind participants, based on EVC activity. This suggests
517 that reach representation in this region is supported by some form of a large-scale
518 organization, as only such representation is likely to be generalizable across the participants.
519 Arguably, the retinotopic organization is the most plausible candidate for such a large-scale
520 representational mechanism in EVC, also in blind individuals (Striem-Amit et al., 2015;
521 Norman and Thaler, 2019; Vetter et al., 2020). Second, we directly confirmed the importance
522 of the EVC retinotopic organization in supporting reach representation in blind individuals by
523 showing that reach direction is preferential represented in typically foveal EVC areas in blind
524 participants. Overall, our results suggest that action-related information can be represented
525 in the EVC through modulation of specific retinotopic locations, and that such modulation is a
526 process that is independent of visual imagery and visual experience. A mechanism of
527 projecting spatial properties of environment onto retinotopic organization can, potentially,
528 underlie activations of visual areas in blind participants for many spatial tasks, such as
529 localizing stimuli in space (Gougoux et al., 2005; Collignon et al., 2007; Garg et al., 2007;
530 Collignon et al., 2011), distance or symmetry judgement (Merabet et al., 2004, Bauer et al.,
531 2015), or Braille reading (Sadato et al., 1996; Cohen et al., 1997; Tian et al., 2023).

532 In sighted individuals, performing actions over small objects preferentially involves the foveal
533 EVC, even when participants do not see these objects, and are asked to fixate on a point
534 placed well above them (Monaco et al., 2017). Similarly, we showed that reaching for Braille
535 words placed in some distance from the center of a Braille sheet (the hand starting point)
536 preferentially involves foveal EVC in congenitally blind participants. This shows that, in both
537 populations, action-related information might be projected onto EVC using the same
538 pathways and mechanisms. Furthermore, preferential involvement of foveal EVC,
539 irrespective of the actual position of a target object, might suggest that the action-related

540 projections to EVC are predictive in nature. In this view, action-related information is sent
541 primarily to the foveal visual areas, because foveal vision is critical for guiding and online
542 correction of motor actions. Such a predictive mechanism would fit with our real-world
543 behaviors - we tend to foveate on small objects we want to grasp, even if, at the stage of
544 formulating action intention, these objects are in our peripheral visual field. Such a
545 mechanism seems more efficient than the coding of the actual position of an object - action
546 endpoint - in the visual field, especially given the multitude of saccades and head turns we
547 perform every second. In our study, we show that pathways supporting such a predictive
548 mechanism of aligning action and visual spaces might be preserved in congenitally blind
549 individuals. Perhaps spatial and motor experience is sufficient to make these pathways
550 functional even in the lifelong absence of vision. Another interesting hypothesis is that the
551 index fingertip of blind individuals serves as tactile “fovea” during Braille reading, that, in our
552 task, moves to the different spatial locations, just like eye movements in the sighted. Our
553 successful decoding results in both foveal EVC and FEF/PMd might support this idea.

554 In our previous study with the same group of congenitally blind participants, we
555 demonstrated that the decoding accuracy of natural sounds increases from foveal to
556 peripheral parts of EVC (Vetter et al., 2020). Here, we show an opposite decoding gradient
557 for reach direction, with decoding accuracy being higher in foveal EVC parts. Together,
558 these findings show a precise functional architecture for representing non-visual information
559 in EVC of congenitally blind individuals, which can be activated in a variety of contexts in a
560 way that potentially reflects computational demands of stimuli or tasks.

561 Besides the successful decoding of trials involving different reach directions, we also found
562 that our task elicited univariate activation of EVC in the blind participants, although these
563 effects were rather subtle. Interpretation of univariate responses is challenging, as they can
564 be driven by both action-related processes and reading Braille words (Sadato et al, 1996;
565 Cohen et al., 1997; Tian et al., 2023). However, our design (using different, unrelated, and
566 abstract Braille words in each experimental run), in combination with the decoding procedure

567 (training and testing the classifier on different runs), ensured that the decoding results,
568 critical for this study, are not affected by the Braille word representations. The only decoding
569 analysis in which our design did not preclude finding Braille-related effects was the cross-
570 participant analysis. Interestingly, even in this analysis, we found robust representation of
571 reach direction in EVC in congenitally blind participants, but no representation of different
572 Braille words.

573 The searchlight analysis highlighted a number of dorsal stream areas that preferentially
574 represent reach directions also in sighted individuals (Fabbri et al., 2014). In the sighted
575 population, these areas are known to be critical for visuo-spatial attention and visuo-motor
576 integration (Mishkin et al., 1983; Goodale and Milner, 1992; Kravitz et al., 2011; Gallivan and
577 Culham, 2015). However, certain studies suggest that the representations computed in
578 these areas are not fully dependent on incoming visual information from the retina (e.g.,
579 Prather et al., 2004; Tark and Curtis, 2009; Bernier and Grafton, 2011; Sathian et al., 2011).
580 In congenitally blind participants, shape identification preferentially activates ventral stream
581 areas, whereas location identification preferentially activates dorsal stream areas (Striem-
582 Amit et al., 2012). Furthermore, similar dorsal regions are preferentially involved in guiding
583 hand movements in congenitally blind and sighted participants (Fiehler et al., 2009). Finally,
584 the FEF/PMd is involved in spatial orienting not only in sighted individuals, but also in
585 congenitally blind participants (Garg et al., 2007). In our study, we add to evidence that
586 dorsal stream areas in congenitally blind individuals truly develop representations of space
587 and/or actions, as indicated by these areas' ability to represent different reach directions.

588 Taken together, our results match the findings in sighted individuals, and suggest that the
589 development of action representations in the human brain might be largely independent of
590 visual experience. It is important to note, however, that the action representations in sighted
591 individuals were mostly studied using 3D objects, whereas, in our study, blind participants
592 reached for Braille words. The exact impact of using such stimuli on our results remains to
593 be investigated. A direct comparison of results from congenitally blind and sighted

594 individuals, preferably in a design using typical 3D objects as action targets, would be
595 necessary to address this issue. Such a comparison would allow a more detailed description
596 of similarities and differences in the brain action systems in these two populations.

597 In conclusion, we show that early visual cortex represents action-related information in
598 congenitally blind individuals. This finding demonstrates that neither visual experience nor
599 visual imagery is necessary for such representations to emerge. Furthermore, we
600 demonstrate remarkable similarity of the dorsal action brain networks in congenitally blind
601 and sighted individuals, which calls for rethinking of how these networks develop in the
602 human brain.

603

604 **Author contributions**

605 P.V. and A.A. conceptualized and designed the experiment; P.V. collected the data; Ł.B. and
606 M.W. performed the data analyses; Ł.B. wrote the manuscript; P.V. and A.A. revised the
607 manuscript.

608

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710

711 **Figure legends**

712 **Figure 1. Study design.** (A-B) Congenitally blind participants reached for and read Braille
713 words printed on one of the four edges of the A4 Braille sheet. The participants started each
714 trial with a finger placed on the central “fixation dot”. They moved their hand upon hearing a
715 verbal cue indicating reach direction (“up”, “down”, “right”, “left”). Different, unrelated Braille
716 words referring to abstract concepts were used in each experimental run. (C) Maps of early
717 visual areas, obtained in a separate, retinotopic mapping experiment with sighted
718 participants, were cortex-based aligned to the reconstructions of cortical anatomy of each
719 blind participant, and then transformed into maximum probability maps. Multi-voxel pattern
720 classification was used to decode reach directions from these early visual areas in the blind
721 participants. The classifier was trained and tested on data from different runs, to ensure that
722 reach direction representation is not confounded with Braille word representation. The figure
723 presents maximum probability maps created for one, representative blind participant (a left
724 hemisphere is presented, inflated for visualization purposes). Different colors indicate
725 different early visual areas (V1: red; V2: green; V3: blue), whereas different shades of the
726 same color – different eccentricities (darker shades in foveal areas, lighter shades in
727 peripheral areas).

728

729 **Figure 2. Reach direction can be reliably decoded from the fMRI activity of early visual**
730 **cortex in congenitally blind participants.** Results of the reach direction decoding analysis
731 in motor cortex (MC), early visual cortex (EVC), auditory cortex (AC), and in specific early
732 visual areas. *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, ^t $p = 0.052$, FDR-corrected. Black lines indicate
733 chance level. Error bars represent the standard error of the mean.

734

735

736 **Figure 3. Different reach directions, but not different Braille words, can be decoded**
737 **across the congenitally blind participants, based on activity of motor cortex and early**
738 **visual cortex.** The results of the cross-participant classification of (A) four reach directions
739 and (B) two sets of Braille words used in the study. The classification accuracies are
740 presented for motor cortex (MC), early visual cortex (EVC), and auditory cortex (AC). ** $p <$
741 0.01 , FDR-corrected. A black line indicates chance level. Error bars represent the standard
742 error of the mean calculated across the cross-validation folds (i.e., across the results of
743 decoding with different participants' data used for testing).

744

745 **Figure 4. The foveal-peripheral gradient of reach decoding accuracy in early visual**
746 **cortex of congenitally blind participants.** Results of the reach direction decoding analysis
747 in early visual regions typically representing the foveal visual field, the peripheral visual field,
748 and the far periphery of the visual field. Results are presented for early visual cortex (EVC)
749 and for specific early visual areas *** $p < 0.001$, FDR-corrected. An arrow indicates a
750 significant linear contrast in a repeated-measures ANOVA. A black line indicates chance
751 level. Error bars represent the standard error of the mean.

752

753 **Figure 5. The foveal-peripheral gradient of reach direction decoding in early visual**
754 **cortex in blind participants can be found across a wide range of patches of interest**
755 **sizes.** The figure presents the accuracy of reach direction decoding in early visual cortex
756 (EVC) in congenitally blind participants. The results are presented separately for areas
757 typically representing the fovea, the peripheries, and the far peripheries of the visual field.
758 The analysis was performed in patches of interest (POIs) containing different numbers of
759 vertices. To create POIs containing only subset of vertices, these vertices were randomly

760 drawn from the whole POIs. At each POI size level, the decoding accuracies were averaged
761 across 1000 random draws of vertices for each POI. The symbols above the results indicate
762 significant main effects of EVC eccentricity, and significant linear contrasts for these effects,
763 in repeated-measures ANOVAs ran at each POI size level. * $p < 0.05$, ^t $p < 0.1$. The
764 decoding chance level is equal to 25 % and is not shown. Error bars represent the standard
765 error of the mean, adjusted to properly reflect variability in repeated-measures comparisons,
766 using a method described by Cousineau (2005).

767

768 **Figure 6. Reach direction decoding accuracies for individual blind participants.** The
769 individual data are presented for motor cortex, early visual cortex (EVC), and auditory cortex.
770 Furthermore, the data are presented for specific early visual areas, and for early visual
771 regions that typically represent foveal, peripheral and far peripheral visual fields. Dotted lines
772 indicate chance level.

773

774 **Figure 7. Results of the searchlight analysis of reach direction decoding.** The accuracy
775 of reach direction decoding was averaged across subjects and visualized on an inflated,
776 averaged cortical surface reconstruction for the blind group. A significant above-chance
777 decoding was found throughout the brain. However, the highest decoding accuracy was
778 observed in somatosensory and motor cortices, the foveal early visual cortex, and in the
779 dorsal brain regions, such as superior parietal lobule, intraparietal sulcus, supplementary
780 motor area, or right frontal eye field/dorsal premotor cortex. The significance of the observed
781 effects was confirmed with a threshold-free cluster enhancement (TFCE) approach and
782 Monte Carlo simulation. The statistical threshold was set at $p < 0.05$, corrected for multiple
783 comparisons across the whole cortical surface.

784

785 **Figure 8. The accuracy of reach direction decoding is higher in early visual cortex and**
786 **dorsal visuospatial areas than in canonical language areas.** Results of the reach
787 direction decoding analysis for the five regions: early visual cortex (EVC), frontal eye
788 field/dorsal premotor cortex (FEF/PMd), intraparietal sulcus (IPS), Broca's area, and left
789 superior temporal sulcus/gyrus (STS/STG). Different colors are used to mark different brain
790 networks to which these brain areas are thought to belong. *** $p < 0.001$, * $p < 0.05$, FDR-
791 corrected. A black line indicates chance level. Error bars represent the standard error of the
792 mean.

793

794 **Figure 9. Univariate responses elicited by reaching for and reading Braille words.** (A)
795 Brain regions showing stronger univariate activation during the experimental trials (i.e., when
796 participants were involved in the task) than during the rest periods. The whole-brain analysis
797 was thresholded at $p < 0.001$, uncorrected (no significant activations were detected at the
798 corrected level). (B-D) Activation during the experimental trials, relative to the rest periods, in
799 (B) early visual cortex (EVC), (C) early visual regions that typically represent fovea (EVC
800 fov), peripheries (EVC peri), and far peripheries (EVC far peri) of the visual field, and (D)
801 specific early visual areas. * $p < 0.05$, ^t $p < 0.1$, FDR-corrected. Arrows indicate significant
802 linear contrasts in repeated-measures ANOVAs. Error bars represent the standard error of
803 the mean.

804

805 **Figure 10. Differences in univariate activations across the reach directions.** (A) Results
806 of the whole-brain F-test testing for the differences in univariate responses across the four
807 reach directions. The significance of the observed effects was assessed using a threshold-
808 free cluster enhancement (TFCE) approach and Monte Carlo simulation. The statistical
809 threshold was set at $p < 0.05$, corrected for multiple comparisons across the whole cortical

810 surface. (B) Univariate responses across the four reach directions in early visual cortex
811 (EVC). * $p < 0.05$, FDR-corrected. Error bars represent the standard error of the mean.

812

813 **Figure 11. Testing for the effects of participants' movements on the study results.** (A)

814 Event-related average plots, illustrating unfolding of brain activation during experimental
815 trials, for early visual cortex (EVC), motor cortex (MC), intraparietal sulcus (IPS), and frontal
816 eye field/dorsal premotor cortex (FEF/PMd). The plots were calculated separately for each
817 hemisphere and then averaged. No signal spikes, characteristics of movement artifacts,

818 were observed. (B) The accuracy of reach direction decoding in frontal white matter (region
819 of interest illustrated in the upper panel, Talairach coordinates of its center: 21, 16, 29). (C)

820 Results of searchlight classification of reach directions that used frontal and temporal
821 regions as baseline for significance testing (MC and FEF/PMd were excluded from the
822 mask). In the whole-brain analysis of searchlight effects (left), significance testing was
823 performed with a threshold-free cluster enhancement (TFCE) approach and Monte Carlo
824 simulation. The statistical threshold was set at $p < 0.05$, corrected for multiple comparisons
825 across the whole cortical surface. In the analysis of searchlight effects in specific brain
826 regions (right), significant increases in classification accuracy, relative to baseline regions,
827 were tested with one-sample t-tests. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, ***, $p < 0.001$, FDR-corrected.

828 Error bars represent the standard error of the mean.

A

(Different Braille words in each run)

B

C

Blind participants (N = 9)
Maximum probability maps

MM (LH)

A Decoding reach direction

B Decoding Braille words

EVC — Fovea — Peripheries — Far peripheries

A

TFCE Permutation: z-values
1.65 ■ ■ ■ 3

